

Dissemination: Share confidently

Share & Disseminate

Determine Data Ownership and Intellectual Property

To effectively share data, researchers should first resolve any data ownership issues to confirm that they have approval to share the data. If researchers have questions, they should consult their PI, members of their department administration, or, if needed, the [Office of Technology Development](#).

- **[Intellectual Property Policy](#)**: The rights, those responsibilities, and principles that determine how research data should be handled ultimately belongs to the University.
- **[Research Data Ownership Policy](#)**: The University asserts ownership over research data for projects conducted at the University, under the auspices of the University, or with University resources. The University delegates stewardship of the data to PIs, therefore the PI has full responsibility for data management. Data ownership policies are available from the [Office of the Vice Provost for Research](#).

Review or Create Data Use Agreement(s)

A Data Use Agreement (DUA) is a binding contract between organizations that governs the transfer and use of data. It is an agreement between the data producer and secondary data user(s) and may impose rules for reuse, storage, re-dissemination, and disposal or termination. Find out more information about [initiating and processing DUAs](#).

- **[Incoming Data](#)**: When obtaining data from any third party (e.g., dbGaP, ICPRS). The appropriate Harvard office will help identify any additional special requirements that must be completed prior to accessing the data, as well as conditions for what to do with the data at the end of the project.
- **[Outgoing Data](#)**: When providing Harvard data to a third party, the Harvard sending party must prepare a DUA with input from appropriate Harvard offices. Data may be transmitted to the Data Recipient in accordance with the DUA terms and conditions.

Fulfill Data Sharing Requirement(s)

There may be requirements from funders and publishers to provide access to research data.

- **[Funder Data Sharing Policies](#)**: SPARC resource of current federal funding agency data sharing policies.
- **[Journal Data Sharing Policies](#)**: CHORUS resources indexing publisher data sharing policies.
 - Publishers have Data Availability Policies at the publisher level or at the journal level. Typically, authors must provide a Data Availability Statement published as part of the accepted article.

Apply Open Science Practices

Sharing all aspects of your research data and protocols is important for open and reproducible science. Here are some helpful resources to get started and practice open science:

- **[Open Access Publishing](#)**: The free unrestricted online access to scientific and scholarly research
 - Publish in an open access peer-reviewed journals (e.g., [Directory of Open Access Journals](#))
 - Deposit in an open access repository (e.g., [Digital Access to Scholarship at Harvard](#); [Preprint repositories](#))
- **[Open Materials and Methods](#)**: Open methods, protocols, and materials facilitate replication and reuse
 - **[Protocols](#)**: Sharing experimental methods and step-by-step protocols supports reproducibility
 - **[Reagents](#)**: Reagent repositories help support validating and sharing reagents

★ **[protocols.io](#) is a collaborative platform for publishing step-by-step methodologies**

The Countway Library offers protocols.io Premium for the HMS/HSDM/HSPH research community. Premium accounts expand access to private and secure workspaces, increased storage capacity, and dedicated support.

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Publish & Reuse

Connect Scholarly Products

Consider ways to link access of your research outputs with persistent identifiers (PIDs). A PID is a long-lasting digital reference to a contributor, organization, or object.

- **People:** [Open Researcher and Contributor ID](#) (ORCID) is an alphanumeric code to uniquely identify scientific and other academic authors and contributors. ORCIDs can be linked to many other profiles.
- **Organizations:** [Research Organization Registry](#) (ROR) aims to provide a persistent identifier for every research organization in the world.
- **Works:** [Digital Object Identifier](#) (DOI) is a persistent identifier or handle used to uniquely identify various objects, including articles, conference proceedings, datasets, research materials, etc.
- **Resources:** [Research Resource Identifiers](#) (RRID) help researchers cite key resources, including antibodies, model organisms, cell lines, plasmids, software tools, and databases.

Select Appropriate Data Repository(ies)

[Data repositories](#) are the preferred method for sharing because they support the discovery, access, and long-term availability of data. Choose the appropriate repository(ies) for all your data types.

- **[Domain-Specific Repository](#):** Have a specific focus, either by data type or by biomedical research discipline. These are good first choices for your data. Examples: NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO), NCBI Database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP), NIMH Data Archive (NDA).
- **[Generalist Repository](#):** Accept data regardless of data type, discipline, or affiliation. These may be used when there isn't an established repository for your data, or you need to share more general data or materials. Examples: Open Science Framework, figshare, Zenodo, Vivli.
- **Institutional Repository:** Focused on preserving and disseminating the scholarship produced by the institution's faculty and students. Example: [Harvard Dataverse](#)

★ Follow the [Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative \(GREI\)](#)

GREI brings together seven NIH-recognized platforms for sharing NIH-funded research data. Harvard provides support for three of these recognized platforms: [Harvard Dataverse](#), [Open Science Framework](#), and [Vivli](#). Utilize the comparison and flow charts to determine the best generalist repository for your research data.

Confirm FAIR Data Principles

To advance science efficiently and ensure reproducibility, follow the [FAIR Data Principles](#):

- **Findable:** Make sure your data can be found – by both humans and search engines.
 - Use repositories to make data searchable and discoverable online, provide structured metadata descriptions, and assign a unique and persistent identifier (e.g., DOI).
- **Accessible:** Tell – both humans and machines – how they can get access to your data.
 - Most published research data is open and available for immediate download. If data cannot be open (e.g., because it contains sensitive information), describe the restrictions and how to request access.
- **Interoperable:** Ensure your data can be integrated with other data and utilized by applications.
 - Avoid sharing proprietary files, using open formats to facilitate easy access and reuse. Use controlled vocabularies and well-defined models to ensure data are well-structured.
- **Reusable:** Make sure data – and related metadata – are well-described.
 - Provide documentation at both the study level and file level. Remove ambiguity about what others can and can't do with your data by assigning a license (e.g., [Creative Commons Zero](#)), and provide a citation to make it easier for others to cite your work.